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A PRELIMINARY CHECKLIST OF BIRDS OF SAJJANGARH WILDLIFE SANCTUARY

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Abstract

The most beautiful, widely admired, more entertaining and most studied group on the animals of the earth is "BIRDS". In capturing our imagination they regime supreme and thus have done more to promote wildlife conservation and care of environment than all other capture put together. Though the Indian subcontinent is gifted with rich diversity of bird life and an equally diverse set of habitat types, our knowledge on the subject is still elementary (Ali and Ripley, 1983). Moreover, species richness and community structure of birds vary from region to region (Recher, 1969; Pearson, 1975 and Karr, 1976) as well as within a region, as abiotic and biotic factors vary from habitat to habitat. The variety is enormous and 8600 species of birds have been estimated over the world by Ali (1941).

Keywords: Preliminary, Environment, Bird, Region

INTRODUCTION

Woodcock (1980) has estimated nearly 1250 species of birds from Indian subcontinent while Grimmet *et al.* (1998) documented 1300 species of birds in the same geographical area. About 510 species of birds can be seen in the state of Rajasthan (Grimmet and Inskipp, 2003). The southern part of Rajasthan is lush green, which supports great avian diversity and the present study area falls into this zone of the state. Lot off work on the avian fauna of various wildlife sanctuaries of Rajasthan has been carried out but still Sajjangarh Wildlife Sanctuary remained untouched. Except for a few documentations no systematic and ecological data regarding to avian fauna are available in the scientific literature.

Sajjangarh Wildlife Sanctuary does not enclose any fresh water body within its limits. But the sanctuary is supported by a peripheral lake ecosystem named Lake Bari which lies in close proximity on the western boundary. The obligatory freshwater lake species as well as large number of terrestrial birds are also dependent on the lake system. Birds have a tendency to go in

surrounding areas and return back. When they go outside they use lake as water hole. A unique combination of terrestrial as well as aquatic habitat supports a variety of bird species thereby forming a part of IBA site. Therefore the present study was carried out to document the avian species in this sanctuary and its surroundings that form an IBA.

STUDY AREA

Sajjangarh Wildlife Sanctuary is the smallest amongst the 25 wildlife sanctuaries of the largest state of Indian Union in terms of area. Sajjangarh Wildlife Sanctuary is in close proximity situated only 5 kms away from the heart of the most romantic city, Udaipur. It is a recently established one, notified as a wildlife sanctuary vide Government of Rajasthan Notification No. F11 (64)/Raj8/86 dated 17.02.1978 under the provision of Section 18 of Wildlife (Protection) Act, 1972 (Central Act No.53). The main criteria behind the declaration of the area as a wildlife sanctuary were its environmental as well as ecological importance. Sajjangarh Wildlife Sanctuary spreads over an area of 5.19 km² including only one forest block Sajjangarh. Area of the sanctuary is entirely enclosed with stone wall and forms one single range called Sajjangarh Wildlife Range (Bhatnagar and Gupta, 2003). There are only two protected areas in Rajasthan that are surrounded by walls - one is Keoladeo National Park, Bharatpur and the other is Sajjangarh Wildlife Sanctuary itself.

Geographically, it is situated between 73° 39' - 73 ° 40' East longitudes and 24° 35' - 24° 39' North latitudes. Altitude varies from 630 - 936m above MSL. The periphery of the sanctuary is constituted by Udaipur City and three villages namely Hawala, Bari, and Gorella which lie adjacent to its boundaries. Five other villages namely Sisarma, Kodiyat, Barda, Morvania and Rampura (Ratakhet) are in 5 kms range and fall into the zone of influence of the sanctuary. Udaipur city is on the south- eastern side of the sanctuary while on its western, northern and southern aspects, the villages Gorella, Bari and Hawala are situated respectively. The villagers inhabiting these villages are dependent directly or indirectly on the sanctuary.

The sanctuary area lies in one of the oldest geological formation in the world – the Aravallis. It is situated atop the Bansdara Hill in the most fragile ecosystem of Aravallis. Once there was a time when this Bansdara Hill was having dense vegetation and thick forest cover.

The area was rich in wildlife and natural resources during those times. Tigers were reported in the area till around the middle of 20th century (Dr. Satish Sharma, pers.com.). The area currently within the limits of sanctuary was used as ‘*Shikargaha*’ (hunting ground) by the erstwhile rulers. Seven shooting boxes (commonly known as ‘*Odhis*’) were constructed around the hills to facilitate hunting. Unfortunately, the over exploitation and non-judicious harnessing of biological and non-biological resources of the Aravallis in the name of rapid development much beyond the sustainable limits, has left the Bansdara Hills in a much precarious condition.

METHODOLOGY:

Primary data collection

One of the most critical and most basic aspects of the problem is to provide an answer to “How many”. Birds live in different habitats, have varied social structures and also show behavioural responses. Birds may live in open areas like grasslands or agricultural systems, and are easier to see. Conversely, they may inhabit dense vegetation, which obstruct a straightforward view. Some birds may be gregarious and may live in flocks of thousands, whereas other may be solitary or in pairs. Counting birds using visual observations, calls, and other indirect methods is fascinating and challenging. To analyze avian diversity (species richness) of Sajjangarh Wildlife Sanctuary, the Timed Species Count method was used.

Timed Species Count Method

This method was developed by Pomeroy and Tenengecho (1986). They assumed that in a bird survey, common species are generally detected earlier than rare forms. Therefore the time taken to detect a bird becomes a measure of its abundance.

The observer walks through the study area at a slow pace for one hour. This one-hour observation period is divided into six 10 minutes time periods. All the species seen in the first 10 minutes time period are recorded. In the next 10 minutes period of the remaining 50 minutes, only those species not seen earlier are recorded. The idea, therefore, is to record a species only once in its appropriate time period. In this way, all earlier observed species are ignored in subsequent time periods.

Analysis

All species recorded are ranked according to their time period. Thus, species recorded in first 10 minutes interval are ranked 6 followed by 5 for the species recorded in the second 10 minutes interval and so on. Unrecorded species are ranked 0. An index of relative abundance of species across all survey visit to the site, therefore, score between a maximum value of six and a minimum value of 1.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A total number of 129 bird species were encountered and identified during the present study. A checklist of the terrestrial birds is given below in Table 1. some of the common terrestrial and arboreal birds observed in and around the sanctuary area in the present study. Grimmett *et al.*, (1999), have documented the variety of birds of Indian Subcontinent in their treatise “Birds of Indian Subcontinent”. The update nomenclature, which is adopted by Grimmett *et al.* (1999) has been followed in present work. The arrangement of taxa in families is carried out by following Ali and Ripley (1983) pattern. Table 2 shows the checklist of aquatic birds observed during the present study.

Table 1: Checklist of terrestrial birds in and around Sajjangarh Wildlife Sanctuary

S.NO.	Family	Scientific Name	English Name	Species Rank (TSC)	Frequency of Species (TSC)*	Local Status**
1	Accipitridae	<i>Elanus</i>	BLACK-SHOULDERED	2	C	R
		<i>caeruleus</i>	KITE	1	MC	R
		<i>Milvus</i>	BLACK KITE	1	MC	R
		<i>migrans</i>	SHIKRA	6	VR	R
		<i>Accipiter</i>	LONG-BILLED	6	VR	R
		<i>badius</i>	VULTURE	6	VR	R
		<i>Gyps indicus</i>	RED-HEADED	4	UnC	R
		<i>Sarcogyps</i>	VULTURE			

S.NO.	Family	Scientific Name	English Name	Species Rank (TSC)	Frequency of Species (TSC)*	Local Status**
		<i>calvus</i> <i>Gyps</i> <i>bengalensis</i> <i>Neophron</i> <i>percnopterus</i>	WHITE-RUMPED VULTURE EGYPTIAN VULTURE			
2	Phasianidae	<i>Francolinus pictus</i> <i>Fracolinus pondicerianus</i> <i>Pavo cristatus</i> <i>Perdicula asiatica</i> <i>Galloperdix spadicea</i>	PAINTED FRANCOLIN GREY FRANCOLIN INDIAN PEA FOWL JUNGLE BUSH QUAIL RED SPUR FOWL	4 3 1 4 6	UnC LC MC UnC VR	R R R R R
3	Charadriidae	<i>Vanellus indicus</i>	RED-WATTLED LAPWING	1	MC	R
4	Burhinidae	<i>Burhinus oedicnemus</i>	EURASIAN THICK-KNEE	3	LC	R
5	Columbidae	<i>Columba livia</i> <i>Streptopelia decaocto</i> <i>Streptopelia tranquebarica</i>	ROCK PIGEON EURASIAN COLLARED DOVE RED COLLARED DOVE	1 1 3 3 4	MC MC LC LC UnC	R R R R R

Karnika Jani / A Preliminary Checklist of Birds of Sajjangarh Wildlife Sanctuary

S.NO.	Family	Scientific Name	English Name	Species Rank (TSC)	Frequency of Species (TSC)*	Local Status**
		<i>Streptopelia chinensis</i>	SPOTTED DOVE			
		<i>Streptopelia senegalensis</i>	LAUGHING DOVE			
6	Psittacidae	<i>Psittacula eupatria</i>	ALEXANDRINE PARAKEET	2 1	C MC	R R
		<i>Psittacula krameri</i>	ROSE-RINGED PARAKEET	3	LC	R
		<i>Psittacula cyanocephala</i>	PLUM-HEADED PARAKEET			
7	Cuculidae	<i>Eudynamys scolopacea</i>	ASIAN KOEL	2	C	R
		<i>Centropus sinensis</i>	GREATER COUCAL	2	C	R
8	Strigidae	<i>Bubo bubo</i>	EURASIAN EAGLE	4	UnC	R
		<i>Athene brama</i>	OWL	3	LC	R
			SPOTTED OWLET			
9	Caprimulgidae	<i>Caprimulgus asiaticus</i>	INDIAN NIGHTJAR	2	C	R
		<i>Caprimulgus affinis</i>	SAVANNA NIGHTJAR	4	UnC	R
10	Apodidae	<i>Apus affinis</i>	HOUSE SWIFT	2	C	R

S.NO.	Family	Scientific Name	English Name	Species Rank (TSC)	Frequency of Species (TSC)*	Local Status**
		<i>Tachymarptis melba</i>	ALPINE SWIFT	5	R	R
11	Alcedinidae	<i>Halcyon smyrnensis</i>	WHITE-THROATED KING FISHER	2	C	R
		<i>Ceryle rudis</i>	PIED KINGFISHER	3	LC	R
12	Meropidae	<i>Merops orientalis</i>	GREEN BEE- EATER	1	MC	R
13	Coraciidae	<i>Coracias benghalensis</i>	INDIAN ROLLER	2	C	R
		<i>Coracias garrulous</i>	EUROPEAN ROLLER	6	VR	PM
14	Upupidae	<i>Upupa epops</i>	COMMON HOOPOE	2	C	R
15	Bucerotidae	<i>Ocyrceros birostris</i>	INDIAN GREY HORNBILL	3	LC	R
16	Megalaimidae	<i>Megalaima haemacephala</i>	COPPERSMITH BARBET	3	LC	R
17	Picidae	<i>Dinopium benghalense</i>	BLACK-RUMPED FLAMEBACK	2	C	R
18	Alaudidae	<i>Mirafra erythroptera</i>	INDIAN BUSHLARK	3	LC	R
		<i>Eremopterix grisea</i>	ASHY-CROWNED SPARROW LARK	2	C	R

Karnika Jani / A Preliminary Checklist of Birds of Sajjangarh Wildlife Sanctuary

S.NO.	Family	Scientific Name	English Name	Species Rank (TSC)	Frequency of Species (TSC)*	Local Status**
19	Hirundinidae	<i>Hirundo</i>	DUSKY CRAG	1	MC	R
		<i>concolor</i>	MARTIN	3	LC	R
		<i>Hirundo</i>	WIRE-TAILED	2	C	R
		<i>smithii</i>	SWALLOW			
<i>Hirundo</i>	RED-RUMPED	2	C	R		
<i>daurica</i>	SWALLOW					
20	Laniidae	<i>Lanius vittatus</i>	BAY-BACKED	4	UnC	R
		<i>Lanius</i>	SHRIKE	2	C	R
		<i>meridionalis</i>	SOUTHERN-GREY SHRIKE			
21	Oriolidae	<i>Oriolus oriolus</i>	EURASIAN GOLDEN ORIOLE	3	LC	R
22	Sturnidae	<i>Sturnus</i>	BRAHMINY	2	C	R
		<i>pagodarum</i>	STARLING	2	C	WM
		<i>Sturnus roseus</i>	ROSY STARLING	6	VR	R
		<i>Sturnus contra</i>	ASIAN PIED	1	MC	R
		<i>Acridotheres</i>	STARLING	4	UnC	R
		<i>tristis</i>	COMMON MYNA			
		<i>Acridotheres</i>	BANK MYNA			
23	Dicruridae	<i>Dicrurus</i>	BLACK DRONGO	1	MC	R
		<i>macrocerus</i>	WHITE-BELLIED	4	UnC	R

S.NO.	Family	Scientific Name	English Name	Species Rank (TSC)	Frequency of Species (TSC)*	Local Status**
		<i>Dicrurus caerulescens</i>	DRONGO			
24	Corvidae	<i>Dendrocitta vagabunda</i>	RUFOUS TREEPIE	2	C	R
		<i>Corvus splendens</i>	HOUSE CROW	1	MC	R
		<i>Corvus splendens</i>	LARGE-BILLED CROW	3	LC	R
		<i>Corvus macrorhynchos</i>				
25	Campephagidae	<i>Tephrodornis pondicerianus</i>	COMMON WOODSHRIKE	3	LC	R
		<i>Pericrocotus cinnamomeus</i>	SMALL MINIVET	3	LC	R
		<i>Pericrocotus erythropygus</i>	WHITE-BELLIED MINIVET	6	VR	R
26	Pycnotidae	<i>Pycnonotus cafer</i>	RED-VENTED BULBUL	1	MC	R
27	Muscicapidae	<i>Turdoides caudatus</i>	COMMON BABBLER	1	MC	R
		<i>Turdoides malcolmi</i>	LARGE GREY BABBLER	1	MC	R
		<i>Turdoides striatus</i>	BABBLER	3	LC	R
		<i>Rhipidura</i>	JUNGLE BABBLER	2	C	R
			WHITE-BROWED FANTAIL	3	LC	R
				1	MC	WM
			WHITE-THROATED	1	MC	R

Karnika Jani / A Preliminary Checklist of Birds of Sajjangarh Wildlife Sanctuary

S.NO.	Family	Scientific Name	English Name	Species Rank (TSC)	Frequency of Species (TSC)*	Local Status**
		<i>aureola</i>	FANTAIL	2	C	R
		<i>Rhipidura</i>	GREY-HEADED	3	LC	WM
		<i>albicollis</i>	CANARY	2	C	R
		<i>Culicicapa</i>	FLYCATCHER	1	MC	R
		<i>ceylonensis</i>	ASHY PRINIA	4	UnC	WM
		<i>Prinia socialis</i>	COMMON	1	MC	R
		<i>Orthotomus</i>	TAILORBIRD	4	UnC	WM
		<i>sutorius</i>	COMMON			
		<i>Phylloscopus</i>	CHIFFCHAFF			
		<i>collybita</i>	ORIENTAL MAGPIE			
		<i>Copsychus</i>	ROBIN			
		<i>sauularis</i>	INDIAN ROBIN			
		<i>Saxicoloides</i>	VARIABLE			
		<i>fulicata</i>	WHEATEAR			
		<i>Oenanthe</i>	BROWN ROCK-CHAT			
		<i>picata</i>	DESERT WHEATEAR			
		<i>Cercomela</i>				
		<i>fusca</i>				
		<i>Oenanthe</i>				
		<i>deserti</i>				
28	Irenidae	<i>Aegithina</i>	COMMON IORA	3	LC	R
		<i>tiphia</i>				
29	Paridae	<i>Parus major</i>	GREAT TIT	3	LC	R

S.NO.	Family	Scientific Name	English Name	Species Rank (TSC)	Frequency of Species (TSC)*	Local Status**
		<i>Parus xanthogenys</i>	BLACK-LORED TIT	5	R	R
		<i>Parus nuchalis</i>	WHITE-NAPED TIT	1	MC	R

30	Motacillidae	<i>Anthus rufulus</i>	PADDYFIELD PIPIT	3	LC	R
		<i>Anthus campestris</i>	TAWNY PIPIT	3	LC	WM
		<i>Motacilla alba</i>	WHITE WAGTAIL	1	MC	WM
		<i>Motacilla maderaspatensis</i>	WHITE-BROWED WAGTAIL	3	LC	R
		<i>Motacilla flava</i>	YELLOW WAGTAIL	3	LC	WM
		<i>Motacilla cinerea</i>	GREY WAGTAIL	2	C	WM
		31	Nectarinidae	<i>Nectarinia asiatica</i>	PURPLE SUNBIRD	1
32	Zosteropidae	<i>Zosterops palpebrosus</i>	ORIENTAL WHITE-EYE	3	LC	R
33	Ploceidae	<i>Passer domesticus</i>	HOUSE SPARROW	3	MC	R
		<i>Ploceus philippinus</i>	BAYA WEAVER	1	C	R
		<i>Lonchura malabarica</i>	INDIAN SILVERBILL	2	C	R
		<i>Lonchura punctulata</i>	SCALY-BREASTED MUNIA	4	UnC	R

Acronyms:

MC = More Common, C = Common, LC = Less Common, UnC = Uncommon, R = Rare, VR = Very Rare, WM = Winter Migrant, PM=Passage Migrant, R= Resident

Summary of Table 1:

Families reported: 33, Genera reported: 62, Species reported: 91

Frequency-wise number of bird species sighted in different time zones: More Common = 23, Common = 22, Less Common = 25, Uncommon = 12, Rare = 2, Very Rare = 7

Local Status: Winter Migrants = 8, Passage Migrants = 2, Residents = 81

Sajjangarh Wildlife Sanctuary does not enclose any fresh water body within its limits. But the sanctuary is supported by a peripheral lake ecosystem named Lake Bari which lies in close proximity on the western boundary. The obligatory freshwater lake species as well as large number of terrestrial birds are also dependent on the lake system. Birds have a tendency to go in surrounding areas and return back. When they go outside they use lake as water hole. A unique combination of terrestrial as well as aquatic habitat supports a variety of bird species thereby forming a part of IBA site. Udaipur city also embodies a necklace of interconnected lakes that together with sanctuary area forms an IBA site. Many resident as well as winter and summer migrants maintain the health of the lake ecosystem. The wildlife sanctuary forms the catchment area of Lake Ecosystem. The sanctuary and its surrounding rocks are the roosting site for various bird species. The lake provides a comparatively less disturbed and very congenial environment for the winter, summer and passage migrants like Great White Pelican, Ruddy Shelduck, Mallard, Woolly Necked Stork and Common Sand Piper. The diversity of aquatic birds observed in the lake is tabulated in Table 2.

TABLE 2: Aquatic bird diversity of Lake Bari, Udaipur

S.No.	Family	Scientific Name	Common Name	Local Status*
1	Pelecanidae	<i>Pelecanus onocrotalus</i>	GREAT WHITE PELICAN	WM
2	Podicipedidae	<i>Tachybaptus ruficollis</i>	LITTLE GREBE	R
3	Phalacrocoracidae	<i>Phalacrocorax carbo</i>	GREAT CORMORANT	R
4		<i>Phalacrocorax niger</i>	LITTLE CORMORANT	R
5	Ardiidae	<i>Ardea cinerea</i>	GREY HERON	WM
6		<i>Ardeola grayii</i>	INDIAN POND HERON	R
7		<i>Bubulcus ibis</i>	CATTLE EGRET	R
8		<i>Mesophoyx intermedia</i>	INTERMEDIATE EGRET	R
9		<i>Egretta garzetta</i>	LITTLE EGRET	R
10		<i>Ardea purpurea</i>	PURPLE HERON	R
11	Ciconiidae	<i>Mycteria leucocephala</i>	PAINTED STORK	R
12		<i>Anastomus oscitans</i>	ASIAN OPENBILL STORK	R
13		<i>Ciconia episcopus</i>	WOOLY-NECKED STORK	R
14	Threskiornithidae	<i>Threskiornis melanocephalus</i>	BLACK-HEADED IBIS	R
15		<i>Pseudibis papillosa</i>	BLACK IBIS	R

Karnika Jani / A Preliminary Checklist of Birds of Sajjangarh Wildlife Sanctuary

16		<i>Platalea leucorodia</i>	EURASIAN SPOONBILL	R
17	Phoenicopteridae	<i>Phoenicopus ruber</i>	GREATER FLAMINGO	WM
18		<i>Phoenicopus minor</i>	LESSER FLAMINGO	WM
19	Anatidae	<i>Anas clypeata</i>	NORTHERN SHOVELER	WM
20		<i>Tadorna ferruginea</i>	RUDDY SHELDUCK	WM
21		<i>Anas platyrhynchos</i>	MALLARD	WM
22		<i>Aythya ferina</i>	COMMON POCHARD	WM
23		<i>Anas crecca</i>	COMMON TEAL	WM
24			<i>Anser indicus</i>	BAR- HEADED GOOSE
25	Gruidae	<i>Grus antigone</i>	SARUS CRANE	R
26	Rallidae	<i>Porphyrio porphyrio</i>	PURPLE MOORHEN	R
27		<i>Fulica atra</i>	COMMON COOT	R
28		<i>Gallinula chloropus</i>	COMMON MOORHEN	R
29		<i>Amaurornis phoenicurus</i>	WHITE- BREASTED WATERHEN	R
30	Jacanidae	<i>Hydrophasianus</i>	PHEASANT-	R

		<i>chirugus</i>	TAILED JACANA	
31		<i>Metopidius indicus</i>	BRONZE- WINGED JACANA	R
32	Recurvirostridae	<i>Himantopus</i> <i>himantopus</i>	BLACK-WINGED STILT	R
33		<i>Recurvirostra</i> <i>avosetta</i>	PIED AVOCET	WM
34	Rostratulidae	<i>Gallinago gallinago</i>	COMMON SNIPE	WM
35		<i>Charadrius dubius</i>	LITTLE RINGED PLOVER	R
36		<i>Charadrius</i> <i>alexandrinus</i>	KENTISH PLOVER	WM
37		<i>Actitis hypoleucos</i>	COMMON SANDPIPER	WM
38	Laridae	<i>Sterna aurantia</i>	RIVER TERN	R

ACRONYMS: WM = Winter Migrant, R = Resident

Summary of Table 2:

Families: 14, Genera: 32, Species: 38

Local Status of aquatic bird species: Winter Migrants = 14, Residents = 24

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